

1. Plant height and internode elongation ability of Habiganj Aman II.

2. Change of total chlorophyll content of leaves of Habiganj Aman II during flooding.

decreased (Fig. 1). No-N plants were shorter than plants with N before flooding, but elongated more rapidly, indicating that ability of internodes to elongate is influenced more by

submergence depth rather than by N content. The no-N plants had lower final plant height.

Chlorophyll content of the three upper leaves of the no-N plants gradually increased during flooding

(Fig. 2). With added N, chlorophyll content decreased and then increased to slightly more than the initial content. Chlorophyll increased more rapidly in no-N plants than in those with added N. *S*

Pest Control and Management INSECTS

Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) outbreak in Haryana, India

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horváth has attacked rice in Haryana since the early 1970s, and severe outbreaks occurred in 1984-85. We surveyed field

populations of WBPH in villages in Karnal, Kurukshetra, Ambala, Jind, Hisar, and Sirsa Districts in mid-Sep, when pest incidence was high and rice was at panicle emergence stage. Sixty of the 85 villages surveyed had more than 70% infestation and 15 villages had 18% infestation (see table). WBPH population was 100-2,000/hill. PR106 was the most affected variety. Weather was generally warm and humid. *S*

WBPH population intensity in Haryana, India, 1984-85.

District	Block	Villages surveyed (no.)	Villages (no.) with indicated intensity ^a		
			Severe	Moderate	Light
Karnal	Nilokheri	4	4	0	0
	Indri	6	6	0	0
	Karnal	3	2	1	0
	Jundla	5	5	0	0
	Assandh	6	4	1	1
Kurukshetra	Pundri	15	13	1	1
	Kaithal	7	7	0	0
	Sewan	4	4	0	0
	Cheeka	3	1	1	1
	Pehowa	2	1	1	0
Ambala	Ambala	2	1	1	0
	Naraingarh	2	0	1	1
	Bilashpur	1	0	1	0
	Jagadhari	2	0	2	0
Sirsa	Rania	12	5	4	3
	Kalait	4	—	1	3
Hisar	Tohana	4	4	0	0
	Ratia	3	3	0	0
Total		85	60	15	10

^aSevere = fields with one or more hopperburned patches; moderate = fields with yellowing; light no visible symptoms.

Need-based control of yellow stem borer (YSB)

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YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* Wlk. damages rice from tillering to maturity. We compared need-based control of YSB using egg masses as threshold criteria with scheduled control in 1983 and 1984 rainy seasons at NARP farm.

The experiment was in duplicate plots (ABBA method) with seven replications. GR-11 seedlings were transplanted in 50-m² plots. Egg masses were counted in need-based plots at 10-d intervals. When 1 fresh egg mass was observed in any plot, all replications were sprayed with monocrotophos 0.36 kg ai/ ha. In schedule-based control plots, the same insecticide formulation was applied 15, 45, and 60 d after transplanting.

Percentage of deadhearts at maximum tillering, number of whiteheads at reproductive stage, and grain yield were recorded, and the data were statistically and economically analyzed.

In 1983, mean percentage of deadhearts was 2.9 in the need-based treatment and 6.4 in the schedule-based treatment (Table 1). The trend was similar in 1984. The number of whiteheads also was significantly lower in need-based than in schedule-based treatments. The need-based treatment had 10 and 15% higher yield in 1983 and

Table 1. Efficiency of need-based control of YSB compared with schedule-based insecticide application, Gujarat, India, 1983 and 1984.^a

Insecticide application	Mean percentage deadhearts		Mean no. whiteheads		Mean grain yield (t/ha)	
	1983	1984	1983	1984	1983	1984
Need-based	2.9 a	3.6 a	75 a	93 a	3.7 a	5.6 a
Schedule-based	6.4 b	6.0 b	102 b	168 b	3.3 b	4.7 b
't' value	2.54	4.09	2.44	3.16	2.71	8.84

^aSeparation of means in a column at the 5% level.

Table 2. Economics of need-based control of YSB, Gujarat, India.

Insecticide application	Total cost of insecticides and labor ^b (\$/ha)		Gross income (\$/ha)		Net gain over check (\$/ha)		Incremental cost benefit ratio (additional profit per \$ cost)	
	1983	1984	1983	1984	1983	1984	1983	1984
Need-based ^a	38	50	565	863	54	132	0.42	1.64
Schedule-based	36	36	511	730	—	—	—	—

^aThree sprays were necessary in 1983 and four in 1984. ^bLabor cost for sampling and applying insecticides.

1984, and higher net return and cost benefit ratio (Table 2).

The appropriate YSB egg mass

threshold level per unit area should be determined. \mathcal{L}

Virulence of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) populations in South and Southeast Asia: report of a collaborative project

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horváth outbreaks appear to have increased in frequency and severity throughout Asia. Resistant varieties, which should play a key role in WBPH control, have not been developed. More than 400 traditional varieties with WBPH resistance have been identified in greenhouse screening at IRRI and in national programs in South and

Table 1. Summary of damage ratings of varieties with genes for resistance in seedbox screening for WBPH.

Variety	Gene	Reaction ^a at					
		Philippines IRRI	India Tamil Nadu	Indonesia Maros	Korea Suweon	Thailand Bangkok	Vietnam Cantho
N22	<i>Wbph 1</i>	R	R	R	R	R	MR
ARC10239	<i>Wbph 2</i>	R	R	R	R	R	S
IR2035-117-3	<i>Wbph 1 + Wbph 2</i>	R	R	R	MR	R	MR
WC1240	<i>Wbph 1 + 1 recessive</i>	R	R	R	R	R	MR
Colombo	<i>Wbph 2 + 1 recessive</i>	R	R	R	R	R	MR
TN1	None	S	S	S	S	S	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Feeding activity of WBPH female adults as indicated by honeydew excretion (area of honeydew spot in mm²)^a on varieties with different genes for resistance.

Variety	Honeydew spot (mm ²)					
	Philippines IRRI	India Coimbatore	Indonesia Maros	Korea Suweon	Thailand Bangkok	Vietnam Cantho
N22	28 a	77 b	3 a	6 a	9 a	47 ab
ARC10239	21 a	95 b	5 a	7 a	45 a	69 b
IR2035-117-3	10 a	8 a	4 a	0 a	46 a	—
WC1240	44 a	14 a	26 a	2 a	41 a	23 a
Colombo	27 a	37 ab	5 a	0 a	151 b	42 ab
TN1	714 b	367 c	116 b	49 b	269 c	121 c

^aAv of 5 replications. Separation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.